

Transformation versus Phase Only Calculation of Generalized Oscillator Propagator

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In a previous note (1), we utilized a transformation of $y=x-b(t)/m$ together with a phase $\exp(i \int_0^t c(t_1) dt_1) \exp(i \int y db/dt)$ factor to solve a time dependent quantum oscillator problem with an extra potential $f(t)x$. In this note, we consider the problem of a generalized oscillator for which a propagator $K_0(x,x_1,t)$ is known. The extra potential $f(t)xW(x,t) + ig(t)dW/dx$ is added and a new propagator found using a transformation $y=x-b(t)/m$ together with two phase factors $\exp(i \int y db/dt) \exp(i \int y db_1/dt)$. This approach is compared to that of (2) for which a solution is obtained using $K(x,x_1,t)=K_0(x,x_1,t) \exp(i a(t)x + i B(t)x_1 + iG(t))$.

The transformation/cancellation approach leads to two differential equations while the method of (2) leads to three differential equations involving various integrations. Both approaches may require numerical solutions.

The Hamiltonian considered in this note is used in quantum modeling of biological systems.
(3)

Propagator for a Generalized Oscillator

Following (2), we consider the Schrodinger equation:

$$i d/dt (\partial) W(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2} (1+\cos 2t) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + \frac{1}{2}(1-\cos 2t)xx W -i/2 \sin 2t (2xdW/dx + W) \quad (1)$$

The propagator for ((1)) is given by (2):

$$K_0(x,x_1,t) = 1/ \{ \sqrt{2*3.14 i [\cos(t) \sinh(t) + \sin(t)\cosh(t)]} \} \exp\{ [(xx-x_1x_1)\sin(t)\sinh(t) - (xx-yy)\cos(t)\cosh(t)] / [2i (\cos(t)\sinh(t) + \cosh(t)\sin(t))] \} \quad (2)$$

An extra potential time wavefunction of $xf(t) W + ig(t) dW/dx$ ((3)) is added to ((1)). In (2), the approach to solving ((2)) plus ((3)) is to introduce:

$$K(x,x_1,t) = K_0(x,x_1,t) \exp(i a(t)x + i B(t)x_1 + i G(t)) \quad (4)$$

((4)) is inserted into ((1)) plus ((3)) and the explicit form of K_0 ((2)) used to solve the problem as dK_0/dx appears. Coefficients of x and x_1 and also pure time components are collected to arrive at three interlinked differential equations.

The results (2) are:

$$a(t) = 1/[\cos(t)\sinh(t) + \sin(t)\cosh(t)] \int_0^t ds \{f(s)[\cos(s)\sinh(s)+\cosh(s)\sin(s)] + g(s)[\cos(s)\cosh(s) - \sin(s)\sinh(s)] \} ds \quad (5a)$$

$$B(t) = \text{Integral } (0,t) \{ (1+\cos(2s))a(s) - g(s) \} / \{ \cos(s)\sinh(s) + \sin(s)\cosh(s) \} ds \quad ((5b))$$

$$G(t) = \text{Integral } (0,t) \{ a(s)g(s) - .5(1+\cos(2s)) a(s)a(s) ds \} \quad ((5c))$$

Transformation/Cancelation Approach

We suggest a transformation $y=x-b(t)/m$ (with $m=1$) together with added phases $\exp(i \text{Integral } (0,t) c(t) dt) \exp(i y db/dt) \exp(i y db_1/dt)$. Two functions $b(t)$ and $b_1(t)$ are needed to deal with $f(t)$ and $g(t)$. In (1), it was shown that for the usual quantum oscillator with an extra $f(t)x$ potential, use of $b(t)$ sufficed. (We show later that even if $g(t)=0$, $b(t)$ and $b_1(t)$ are needed given the nature of ((1))). The first phase factor with $\text{Integral } (0,t)$ handles purely time dependent terms.

The idea used here is to employ a transformation to force one term from id/dt partial W to yield dW/dy $(-db/dt)$ because the RHS of ((1)) contains an operator $-1/2m d/dy d/dy$ which yields a term $-1/m dW/dy d/dy$ $(\exp(i y \text{ phase}))$ in addition to a piece $-i \sin(2t) 2b/m dW/dy$ and finally $ig(t) dW/dy$. We choose a solution such that these terms cancel which yields a differential equation in $db(t)/dt$, $b(t)$ and $db_1/dt(t)$ in terms of $g(t)$. This is the first differential equation.

The next issue is to deal with the term $yf(t)$ i.e. find linear terms in y . This yields a second differential equation in $b(t)$ and $b_1(t)$ or derivatives.

In the above paragraph, one may substitute W with $Ko(x,x_1,t)$ because both are solutions of the Schrodinger equation ((1)). We set $m=1$ as in (2).

First Differential Equation

One term of $id/dt \{ \exp(i \text{Integral}(0,t) c(t)dt) \exp(i y db/dt) \exp(i y db_1/dt) Ko(x-b,x_1,t) \}$ is:

$-i dKo/dy (db/dt)$ (i.e this is the term with d/dt acting on Ko)

On the RHS: $-(1+\cos(2t)) dKo/dy (i db/dt + i db_1/dt) -i \sin(2t) b dKo/dy + i g(t) dKo/dy$ Or:

$$-db/dt = -(1+\cos(2t))(db_1/dt + db/dt) - \sin(2t)b + g(t) \quad ((6))$$

Second Differential Equation

Next, one considers terms linear in y :

From $i d/dt \exp(i \text{ phase})$ one has $-y (d/dt db/dt + d/dt db_1/dt)$

The RHS yields: $-fy + \sin(2t) y (db/dt + db_1/dt) + (1-\cos(2t))by$ or

$$-(d/dt db/dt + d/dt db_1/dt) - \sin(2t)(db/dt + db_1/dt) = -f(t) + (1-\cos(2t)) b \quad ((7))$$

Equation ((6)) yields: $db/dt + db_1/dt = \{db/dt - \sin(2t)b + g\} / \{1+ \cos(2t)\} \quad ((6b))$

Differentiating ((6b)) by d/dt yields $P(d/dt db/dt, db/dt, b, t)$ which may be inserted into ((7)) yielding a second order DE in b which may be solved.

$$A(t) d/dt db/dt + B(t) db/dt + C(t) b + D(t) = 0 \text{ with } E(t) = (1 + \cos(2t)) \quad ((7b))$$

$$A(t) = -1/E(t) \quad B(t) = 2\sin(2t)/(E(t)E'(t))$$

$$C(t) = (-1 + \cos(2t)) + \sin(2t)\sin(2t)2/(E(t)E'(t)) + \sin(2t)\sin(2t)/E(t) + 2\cos(2t)/E(t)$$

$$D(t) = f(t) - \sin(2t) g(t)/E(t) - 2g(t)\sin(2t)/(E(t)E'(t)) - dg/dt / E(t)$$

With $b(t)$ known by solving ((7b)) (probably numerically), ((6)) yields $b_1(t)$.

From a physical point of view, ((8)) shows the nature of the transformation $y = x - b(t)$.

The term $c(t)$ is given by all pure time pieces i.e.

$$c(t) = b (db/dt + db_1/dt) + f(t)b + .5(1 + \cos(2t)) (db/dt + db_1/dt)(db/dt + db_1/dt) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos(2t))bb - g(t) [db/dt + db_1/dt]$$

If $g(t) = 0$, $b_1(t)$ and $b(t)$ are still needed. In that case, one has the two equations in two unknown functions. The first can be used to solve for db_1/dt which may be used in the second.:

$$-db/dt = -(1 + \cos(2t))(db_1/dt + db/dt) - \sin(2t)b$$

$$-(d/dt db/dt + d/dt db_1/dt) - \sin(2t)(db/dt + db_1/dt) = -f(t) + (1 - \cos(2t)) b$$

Discussion

It seems ((7)) and ((8)) may need to be solved numerically, but we argue that the solution of (2) may also require numerical solution. Thus, neither approach yields simple solutions. We argue that the transformation approach may highlight a kind of collective motion present in the system. For example, for the simpler Schrodinger equation:

$$id/dt (\text{partial}) W = -1/2m d/dx d/dx W + .5kx^2 W + f(t) x W \quad ((9))$$

The transformation approach yields a solution of $W_n(y) \exp(i \int_0^t c(t_1) dt_1) \exp(iy db/dt)$ where $W_n(y)$ are oscillator eigenfunctions. Thus, one sees the quantum eigenfunction behaviour with a changing origin $y = x - b(t)/m$ and additional phases. The approach of (2) may also be applied to the propagator of ((9)) i.e. $K(x, x_1, t) = K_o(x, x_1, t)$ where K_o represents the oscillator, but

one does not see the same physics as $K_0(x, x_1, t)$ represents oscillator propagation in x, t not in the y frame.

Conclusion

We present an alternative approach, namely a transformation approach to (2) for solving for a generalized oscillator Schrodinger equation ((1)) with the added potential * wavefunction: $f(t)xW + ig(t)dW/dx$. This approach involves two coupled differential equations, while that of (2) involves three. These three, however, may be written as integral equations although a numerical approach may be needed for both methods depending on the form of $f(t)$ and $g(t)$. The transformation approach, however, may yield insight into collective motion i.e. a frame $y=x-b(t)/m$ in the problem. The Schrodinger equation ((1)) with the added potential ((3)) is used to model quantum mechanics in certain biological systems (3).

References

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